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Research Paper

Design And Development of Anti-Inflammatory Cream from Prepared Medicated Oil of *Moringa Oleifera*

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ABSTRACT

Moringa oleifera, often referred to as the "Miracle Tree," is known for its vast range of medicinal properties, including anti-inflammatory activity. This study aimed to design and develop an anti-inflammatory cream using medicated oil derived from *Moringa oleifera* leaves. Phytochemical screening of the aqueous extract of *M. oleifera* leaves revealed the presence of flavonoids, tannins, saponins, alkaloids, glycosides, and volatile oils. In vitro anti-inflammatory activity was assessed using the protein denaturation inhibition assay, demonstrating a significant inhibition rate of 49.25% at 800 µg/ml, comparable to standard Ibuprofen at the same concentration. The results suggest that the formulated herbal cream possesses anti-inflammatory properties, making it a potential natural remedy for inflammation-related skin conditions

INTRODUCTION

Moringa oleifera L. is the most widely cultivated of the 13 species of the family Moringaceae that is native to the sub-Himalayan tracts of India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Afghanistan, and Nepal, which is now indigenous to many regions of Africa, Southeast Asia, and South [1]. A plethora of studies that have been published in the decade describe the popularity of moringa as a "Miracle tree". It is a well-known plant for nutritional as well as potential antioxidant [2], anticancer, anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic, and antimicrobial

agent, and possesses numerous medicinal qualities [3]. The leaves have been established as a rich source of phenolics and glucosinolates [4],[5], carotenoids [6], isothiocyanates [7] and various protein, vitamins, amino acids, and phenolics [8]. Cream containing leaf extract is a natural effective ingredient for improving hydration, which can be used in moisturizing cosmetic formulations and also to complement the treatment of dry skin. [9],[10],[11].

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Table 1: Plant profile of *Moringa oleifera*

Kingdom	Plantae
Division	Magnoliophyta
Class	Magnoliopsida
Subclass	Dilleniidae

Order	Brassicales
Family	Moringaceae
Genus	<i>Moringa</i>
Species	<i>oleifera</i>

Table 2: Reported chemical constituents of *Moringa oleifera* leaves^{[12][13][14]}

Name	Structure
Kaempferol	
Quercetin	
Rutin	
Lutein	
β -carotene	
Niazirin	

Niazirin	
Ellagic acid	
Caffeic acid	
4-(α -L-rhamnopyranosyloxy)benzyl glucosinolate	
Niaziminin	

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection and Authentication of *Moringa oleifera* leaves

The *Moringa oleifera* leaves were collected from Peringottukara, Thrissur, Kerala. The collected herbal leaves were authenticated by Dr. C T Anitha, Head of Department, Department of Botany, Sree Narayana College, Nattika, Thrissur, Kerala

Preparation of medicated oil from *Moringa oleifera* leaves^[15]

The medicated oil was prepared from *Moringa oleifera* leaves using the formula given below.

Rx

Moringa leaves	-	25g
Coconut oil	-	100ml
Water	-	400ml

- Weigh the required amount of crushed moringa leaves and the coconut oil as an oil base.
- Mix base oil with the water in an accurate ratio and add Kalka (paste of herb used, moringa leaves) in it.
- Heat the mixture on low flame till only oil remains. Water and the moisture content get evaporated.
- Do not forget to stir the mixture throughout the process to prevent charring.

- When the oil is ready, leave it for several hours, so that the temperature falls naturally.
- After that, filter the oil and discard the residues. Preserve the oil in a suitable tight container and evaluated its colour, odor, and texture

Preparation of herbal cream from prepared medicated oil^[16]

The cream was prepared using the formula given below.

Rx		
Moringa oil	-	8g
White beeswax	-	3.33g
Borax	-	0.18g
Vitamin E	-	1 capsule
Water	-	6.5ml

Method of preparation

- The required quantity of prepared Moringa oil and beeswax was taken in a China dish and heated in a water bath up to 75°C.
- In another China dish take borax and water, heated up to 75°C.
- Mix both the solution slowly with continuous stirring till a cream-like consistency is obtained.
- Add vitamin E capsule into the cream.
- Pack it in a suitable tight container

Evaluation of the formulated cream

Organoleptic properties

The prepared cream was evaluated for its colour, odour, and texture by manually^[17].

Physicochemical analysis of cream

The physicochemical analysis of cream includes pH, viscosity, homogeneity, appearance, softness, washability, and irritancy^[18].

Preparation and Phytochemical analysis of Moringa leaves extract

Preparation of aqueous extract of leaves

50g of the powdered leaves were weighed and poured into a 250ml conical flask in which 200ml

of distilled water was added. The mixture was kept for 12 hours with constant agitation at 30 minute intervals. The extract was filtered using Whatman No.1 filter paper. The filtrate was concentrated in a Rotary vacuum evaporator. The semi-solid extract obtained was stored in a refrigerator for further use^[18].

Phytochemical analysis of the extract^[19]

1) Test for flavonoids

Shinoda Test: To the extract, add 5ml 95% ethanol, a few drops of conc. Hydrochloric acid and 0.5 g magnesium turnings. Orange, pink, red to purple colour indicate the presence of flavonoids.

2) Test for Tannins

Add few drops of aqueous basic lead acetate solution to 1ml of aqueous solution of crude extract using a test tube. Reddish brown bulky precipitate indicates the presence of tannins.

3) Test for saponins

1g of extract was taken in a test tube containing 5ml of sodium bicarbonate and 5ml of water and the contents were shaken vigorously. The formation of a stable froth suggests the presence of saponins.

4) Test for Alkaloids

Take 5ml solution of extract and then add 2ml of Wagner's reagent to it. The appearance of brown precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids.

5) Test for Glycosides

To 5ml extract add dilute sulphuric acid and boil it for 15 minutes. Cool and neutralize with 10% NaOH, then 5ml of Fehling's solution A and B was added. A brick-red precipitate of reducing sugar indicates the presence of glycosides.

6) Test for Volatile oils

2ml of extract solution was shaken with 0.1ml of sodium hydroxide and a small quantity of dilute HCl. A white precipitate was formed with volatile oils.

In vitro Anti-Inflammatory activity

Inhibition of Protein Denaturation Assay

Protein denaturation results loose of biological properties of protein molecules. Protein denaturation has been correlated with the formation of inflammatory disorders like rheumatoid arthritis, diabetes and cancer. Therefore, ability of substance to prevent the protein denaturation may also help to prevent the inflammatory disorders^[20]. The 0.2 ml of egg albumin was added to vials containing 2.5ml of 0.1M Phosphate Buffer Saline (PBS) pH 6.4. 2 ml of sample was added to vials (in triplicate) to achieve the final concentration of 200, 400, 800 µg/ml. PBS (2.5 ml) and egg albumin were added to control vials. Then, the mixture was incubated at 37°C ± 2°C in an incubator for 15 min and then heated at 70°C for 5 min. After cooling, their absorbance was measured at 660 nm using the vehicle as blank. The percentage inhibition of protein denaturation of the test should be compared with negative control^[21].

% Inhibition of denaturation = $(1-D/C) \times 100$.

Where D is the absorbance of test sample and C is the absorbance of the negative control (without the test sample or reference drug).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Preliminary analysis of Moringa Taila

Table 3: Preliminary analysis of Moringa Taila

Colour	Greenish colour
Odour	Characteristic odour
Touch	Greasy and soft
Consistency	Smooth and homogeneous
Texture	Smooth liquid, opaque

Preliminary analysis of cream

Table 4: Preliminary analysis of cream

Colour	Light green colour
Odour	Characteristic odour
Touch	Greasy and soft
Consistency	Smooth, homogeneous
Texture	Smooth creamy thick, non-gritty

Table 5: Physicochemical analysis of cream

pH	5.6-7.0
Viscosity	2.6-3.7 cps
Homogeneity	The formulation produced uniform distribution of extract in cream. This was confirmed by visual appearance and by touch.
Appearance	Formulation was kept for 3 months, it was found that there was no change in colour of cream.
Softness	Slipperiness, and amount of residue left after the application of the fixed amount of cream were found.
Washability	The cream applied on the skin were easily removed by washing with tap water and showed good washability.
Irritancy	The cream showed no redness, inflammation or irritation during irritancy studies. These formulations are safe to use for skin.

Phytochemical analysis of Moringa leaves extract

Table 6: Phytochemical analysis of Moringa leaves extract

Flavonoids	Present
Tannins	Present
Saponins	Present

Alkaloids	Present
Glycosides	Present
Volatile oil	Present

Inhibition of protein denaturation assay

The effect of aqueous extract of *M. oleifera* leaves in protein denaturation with egg albumin is given in Table 7. The results obtained indicated that the formulation showed significant anti-inflammatory activity by reducing the protein denaturation. The highest inhibition rate was observed at the concentration of 800 µg/ml (Table 7). The observed inhibition rate was comparable with standard Ibuprofen at 800 µg/ml which was 88.88% [22].

Table 7: Percentage inhibition rate of Protein denaturation of aqueous extract of *Moringa oleifera*

Concentration (µg/ml)	Rate of inhibition (%)
200	17.91±3.28
400	31.34±1.20
800	49.25±0.41

Results are shown as mean±SEM. SEM: Standard error of mean

Figure 3: Graph showing the result of Inhibition of protein denaturation assay

CONCLUSION

The present study aims at developing a herbal cream using medicated oil of *Moringa oleifera* leaves. The physicochemical evaluation of the herbal cream was performed. Phytochemical screening of the aqueous extract revealed the presence of flavonoids, tannins, saponins, alkaloids, glycosides and volatile oil. The *in vitro* anti-inflammatory evaluation of the aqueous extract was performed by 'Inhibition of albumin denaturation assay'. The anti-inflammatory activity of the aqueous extract of *Moringa* leaves was found to be 49.25% at the concentration of 800 µg/ml. Hence it was concluded that the medicated oil and the formulated herbal cream possess Anti-Inflammatory activities. Further studies can be directed in order to find out the phytochemical in the plant responsible for the anti-inflammatory action and to develop formulations using it.

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